

1 **Bcl7c participates in germ layer lineage choice of pluripotent stem cells.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
7 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
8 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
9 describe a requirement for Bcl7c in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem cells in *Homo sapiens*.

10 Citations

11 1. Wischhof, L., Lee, H.M., Tutas, J., Overkott, C., Tedt, E., Stork, M., Peitz, M., Brüstle, O., Ulas, T.,
12 Händler, K. and Schultze, J.L., 2022. BCL7A-containing SWI/SNF/BAF complexes modulate mitochondrial
13 bioenergetics during neural progenitor differentiation. The EMBO journal, 41(23), p.EMBJ2022110595.
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